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Sources of Up-to-Date Information of the University Library during the Full-Scale Russian Invasion of Ukraine

Objective. The article aims to highlight the peculiarities of the acquisition process of a university research library in wartime and the qualitative satisfaction of readers' requests with the help of stock collections. The object of the study is the books and journals added to the university's library collections in 2022-2024. The new acquisitions were analysed by type, subject, publisher and source. **Methods.** To create a holistic picture of the development of the library's documentary resource over time, the analytical-synthetic, systemic-structural, comparative and statistical research methods were used. **Results.** The results of the study indicate that the selection and analysis of the university library's acquisitions during the war proves the primary importance of replenishing the book collection with Ukrainian-language multidisciplinary sources of relevant information. This contributes to the quality information support of the educational process and scientific activity in full. **Conclusions.** Despite the difficulties, library collections as an information system are developing and updating. The analysis allowed us to present a picture of the state of Ukrainian publishing and strong support for university libraries.

Keywords: university library; collections; new acquisitions; full-scale Russian-Ukrainian war of 2022–2024; educational process; Ukraine

Introduction

The process of activity of scientific libraries during military operations is a relevant and urgent topic of modern research. Library collections, as an integral part of the state's information resources, attract the attention of scholars, cultural figures, and ordinary citizens. In times of war, there arise challenges and problems that need to be addressed on a daily basis using a holistic system of library collections. During the martial law, since 24 February 2022, the scientific library of the Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (DNU, Dnipro, Ukraine) has continued to operate and provide information support to the educational process. The priority tasks of the library are to preserve the book heritage and to form and strengthen the national and patriotic education of students. The main functions of the library are to meet the diverse reader's needs of higher education students of different categories and teaching staff with the help of funds and their collections. In modern conditions, the library updates the library collections and removes from them publications of the aggressor country with political content. Therefore, it is important to replenish the collection with new, relevant Ukrainian-language literature. Thanks to state programmes of publishing houses, public organisations, and individuals, the stock collections are updated and meet the information needs of the university.

In the course of this study, a certain number of research results were processed. The article by T. S. Yezhyzhanska (2023) is devoted to the activities of Ukrainian publishing houses during the war. The role of the collection as a documentary resource of libraries is presented in a comprehensive monograph by T. O. Dolbenko (2017) and Y. I. Horban (2017). Certain aspects of the work of university libraries, in particular, acquisition and replenishment of funds, promotion of book acquisitions during crisis situations are covered in the works of V. A. Verhunov (2023), O. F. Prokhnenko (2024). The scientific research of O. O. Natarov (2023) is devoted to the activities of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine in disseminating the results of modern scientific research in thorough monographs, defining the essence of the library as an information service system under martial law. An important source of this research is the reporting

documentation of the scientific library in recent years, which contains textual and statistical information about the stock and replenishment of collections (Luchka, 2024). A modern study by J. A. Deineka (2023) highlights the role of US libraries in the processes of information dissemination, the programme of assistance to libraries with books and periodicals during the world wars. The experience of American libraries during the war period is useful for Ukrainian libraries in terms of forms of work on acquisition with the help of grants. The review of recent publications outlines a certain research space on the chosen topic.

The analysis of the literature on this topic allows defining the purpose of the article, which is to highlight the peculiarities of the acquisition process of a scientific library in wartime and the qualitative satisfaction of readers' requests with the help of stock collections.

Methods

In accordance with the tasks set, the study used the analytical-synthetic, systemic-structural, comparative and statistical methods of scientific research. The methodology was used to create a systematic historical and library study, analyse and highlight the main acquisition processes, quantitative composition, and content of the university library by type of literature and language.

Results and Discussion

The collections as an integral documentary resource are aimed at assisting the university community in the educational process. The collections belong to the information system, which is not stable, but is constantly moving, developing and updating. The library acquisition during martial law is problematic, sporadic and incomplete. However, the experience of the scientific library of DNU shows the unity of the library community and its support at the state level. Over the period 2022-2024, the collections of the scientific library were replenished with more than 5 thousand copies of the latest scientific, educational and fiction literature in Ukrainian and foreign languages. New acquisitions help provide users with materials on important topics. According to accounting documents, the largest percentage is made up of scientific publications, followed by textbooks and educational literature. By language: about 90% in Ukrainian, over 10% in foreign languages. By subject matter: historical, philosophical, legal, natural and technical sciences have replenished the collections with professional publications (Dolbenko & Horban, 2017).

Ukraine's publishing policy in the context of war is aimed at opposing Russian propaganda and information manipulation. The academic publications received by the scientific library from more than 25 state publishing houses, institutions and organisations are significant in terms of content and quantity: "Akademperiodyka", "Naukova Dumka", "Helvetica", "Law of Ukraine", "Gerda", M. Lysenko Publishing House (Nizhyn), 6 different institutes of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, The Hetmanate Heritage Foundation, the Ukrainian Institute of National Memory, the National Museum of the Holodomor-Genocide (Kyiv), and the Ukrainian Library Association (Didenko, 2023). Academic publications in astronomy, biology, geology, philosophy, literature, and art are the most thorough and most oriented towards researchers and are intended primarily for the acquisition by national and academic libraries, such as the library of DNU (Fig. 1-4). The publications of the "Naukova Knyha" project are valuable subsidiary projects "Scientific Book. Young Scientists" and "Ukrainian Scientific Book in a Foreign Language", which are in high demand among master's and PhD students. It is worth paying attention to the collection of publications received from the National Museum of the Holodomor-Genocide and dedicated to the tragic pages of the history of the Ukrainian people. These books are interesting as sources of oral

history and provide real facts and testimonies of contemporaries of the era. They are used during lectures and meetings of the DNU Student History Club.

Fig. 1-4.

In 2023, the scientific library received a collection of comprehensive scientific publications on the history of Ukrainian art, ethnography and urban folklore from the M.T. Rytsky Institute of Art Studies, Folklore and Ethnology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. These donations were received as part of the programme “The National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine to Libraries”. The publications are beautifully decorated, illustrative, full of interesting facts, events and personalities. Particular attention should be paid to modern encyclopaedias and reference books that serve as navigators in the wide information space of Ukraine (Yezhzhanska, 2023) (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5.

It is important to note that despite the changes in the format of service, the most important priority is to provide content for library collections, both with complete collections and individual author's copies that are information sources and valuable in the educational process. The formation of high-quality library collections is aimed at the future of education, science, and culture, which, in turn, is associated with their updating and open access to up-to-date information.

Professional publications come from the V. I. Vernadskyi National Library of Ukraine. Among them are scientific monographs on the history of the collections, catalogues of publications, professional collections of scientific works on the history and current state of library science. The collection includes unique research on the history of the Shroud and a catalogue of the collection of the Kyiv Treasury Chamber. The scientific collections “Manuscript and Book

FUNDS OF LIBRARIES

Heritage of Ukraine” and annual issues of “Scientific Works” contain modern research on the preservation of cultural heritage during the war and innovative library processes (Fig. 6-10). As an active participant in the events dedicated to the 150th anniversary of the Taras Shevchenko Scientific Society (Lviv), the Library received substantial anniversary publications (historical essays, encyclopaedia) (*150 rokiv*, 2023).

Fig. 6-10.

The collection of publications received from the All-Ukrainian Ecological League and dedicated to environmental issues during the war is also relevant. The periodicals from the Kyiv Ecological and Cultural Centre are also rich in information and are used by students of the Faculty of Biology and Ecology and the Department of Geography during lectures and practical classes. Under the project “Cooperation with Germany”, the scientific library received about 600 copies, 35 titles of medical and psychological textbooks and recommendations containing relevant information on disease prevention, information technology in medicine, nursing, organisation and methods of volunteer work, prevention of emotional burnout and designed for higher education students during practical classes. A certain part of these publications was prepared with the participation of Oles Honchar Dnipro National University teachers.

An important source of replenishment of the collection is book exchange with colleagues. Thus, thanks to Odesa I. I. Mechnykov National University, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Lviv Polytechnic National University, and V. Karazin Kharkiv National University, the DNU Scientific Library has substantially replenished its collections of periodicals. Bulletins and collections of scientific works of historical and philological content were received from Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University, Western Ukrainian National University, Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv Pedagogical University, Kyiv National University of Construction and Architecture, Uzhhorod National University, and Ternopil Volodymyr Hnatiuk National Pedagogical University (Luchka, 2024).

The collection of local lore publications was substantially replenished with donations from the Dnipro Regional Universal Scientific Library, the Dnipro History Museum, and the Dnipro National History Museum. The donations include literary and journalistic publications, historical works, reference books, and the latest works of famous Dnipro local historians (M. Chaban, F. Sukhonis, N. Bulanova, L. Annenkova).

Educational literature as a toolkit for new disciplines came from Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, V. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Zaporizhzhia National University, Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Ukrainian State University of Science and Technology, and others. Textbooks on biochemistry, physiology, mathematical and physical sciences will be useful for students during the educational process. A certain number of entries in the inventory book of the scientific library are related to donations from individuals from different cities of Ukraine (Kyiv, Dnipro, Ivano-Frankivsk, Lviv, Ternopil, Cherkasy). Valuable in terms of content and relevant in terms of time is the pedagogical publication that the library received from a teacher by profession, Krystyna Torop, dedicated to the psychology of inclusive children

(“Special Stories of the Special: Not Sad Stories”). This publication is about the students of the Special School “Chance” in Dnipro and is useful for students of education, psychology, and medicine.

During the period under review, the university library was replenished with the publications of the Alma Mater, namely textbooks, educational and scientific literature. Among them there are monographs by the academic staff of the Faculty of History, the Faculty of Physics and Technology, the Faculty of Ukrainian and Foreign Philology. These are thorough author and collective monographs that are useful in the educational process and research. The library received new issues of professional journals published by DNU: “Geology, Geography and Geocology”, “Philosophy and Political Science in the Context of Modern Culture”, “Studies in History and Philosophy of Science and Technology”, “Epistemological Studies in Philosophy, Social and Political Sciences”, which contain articles based on the results of research by DNU and Ukrainian scientists on topical issues of geography, geology, philosophy, political science, social and technical sciences. The publications are actively used by researchers and teachers of higher education institutions, as well as postgraduate students and students of specialised faculties. The information resource of the library was replenished with publications from 10 own and personal libraries of DNU professors and prominent figures of the city (Oles Honchar Dnipro National University, 2024).

Collections of scientific papers, bulletins, and scientific journals of DNU, which are included in the world scientometric databases Scopus, WOS, and others, are valuable for scientific research. The annual professional publications are multidisciplinary, have authoritative editorial boards and are rich in relevant materials (Scientific Library of Oles Honchar Dnipro National University, 2024) (Fig. 11-12).

Fig. 11-12.

For an in-depth study of the origins, in order to honour the traditions and customs of the native land, the collections of local lore publications are useful, the research of which has intensified during this period. The scientific library has been replenished with comprehensive serial publications on the history of districts of Dnipro region, individual settlements, and biographical publications. The multi-volume publications “Monuments of History and Culture. Dnipropetrovska oblast” are in high demand. These publications are important sources of local lore, containing detailed descriptions of the region. This beautifully designed and illustrated series is dedicated to the archeology, architecture, history and art of eight communities in the region.

Special attention should be paid to the collections of the foreign publications department, which have been replenished with book collections (the “Unbreakable Libraries” project, from the own libraries of DNU graduates, and the Ukrainian diaspora). In today's environment, an important

area of the library's work is research and in-depth study of the origins of the Ukrainian nation and the life of world-famous Ukrainians. From this perspective, the donated collection of books on the history and culture of the Ukrainian people published abroad by members of the Ukrainian diaspora is meaningful. The transfer of the books was made possible with the assistance of Fidel Sukhonos, a graduate of DNU, head of the Dnipro regional organisation of the National Union of Writers of Ukraine, editor-in-chief of the literary-artistic journal "Borysten". The collection includes scientific publications of the 50s-70s of the twentieth century on history, ethnology, geography, biography, as well as works of art. Some of these copies have unique inscriptions and notes by the owners. Each edition is a real source of knowledge on the history of the country and book publishing for students of different faculties (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13

Valuable gifts were individual copies from the Institute of World Literature of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, the Ukrainian Research Institute of Harvard University, and the University of St. Gallen. In today's context, quarterly issues of journals from the Johns Hopkins University Press (USA), the University of Pennsylvania Press (USA), the Ukrainian Congress Committee of America, and the National Psychological Association for Psychoanalysis have become particularly valuable in terms of content. It was the journals that became relevant sources for the creation of media projects by students of the Faculty of Systems and Mass Communication related to information warfare and fakes ("American Quarterly", "The Ukrainian Quarterly", "American Psychological Association"). "American Quarterly" is a guide to American studies and publishes forums, exhibition and book reviews, as well as short, timely reflections. The modern journal "The Ukrainian Quarterly" not only presents materials and reviews on Ukrainian history, literature, art, politics, and sociology, but also describes current events and international initiatives regarding the Russian-Ukrainian war. The editorial board is responsible for analytical articles, reviews, and correspondence with readers (Fig. 14). The "Journal of the History of Ideas" is a medium for publishing research on intellectual history that is of common interest to scholars and students in many fields. The publication contains materials on intellectual history, including the history of philosophy, literature and art, natural and social sciences, religion and political thought (Project MUSE, n.d.).

Fig. 14.

The fiction collections are in great demand among the university's readers. During martial law in Ukraine, interest in reading Ukrainian literature and works by Ukrainian writers of the nineteenth and early twenty-first centuries increased. The support of publishers, friends of the library and book lovers contribute to the renewal of the collection, which is actively used by students of various faculties. In 2022-2024, the collection was replenished with works by contemporary Ukrainian writers, which are the creative basis for scientific research at the humanities faculties. Among the collections, it is worth noting the Austrian library, which includes works by Austrian and German authors translated into Ukrainian and English.

Each publication received by the scientific library is relevant, useful and interesting for certain reader categories. The library plays an important role in disseminating information about new acquisitions in various forms, including the "Bulletin of New Acquisitions", thematic bibliographic reviews, presentations of collections and individual copies, cooperation with faculty deans, conducting classes with students, and creating thematic lists of contemporary literature for the educational process. In this area, the library's goal is to ensure that each publication finds a readership and becomes useful content in the educational process. Despite the difficulties, the academic library uses various forms and methods to promote its own book collections and create a high-quality information space for the university contingent.

The results of the study show that the selection and analysis of the university library's acquisitions during the war proves the primary importance of replenishing the book collection with Ukrainian-language multidisciplinary sources of relevant information. This contributes to the quality information support of the educational process and research activities in full.

Conclusion

Thus, during the martial law in Ukraine, replenishment of the scientific library's collections is a solid foundation for a quality educational process and an integral part of the cultural and educational development of the city. The support of a scientific library, its proper functioning and successful results are closely linked to the publishing industry and the state policy of disseminating Ukrainian-language literature. The use of modern scientific publications and literary-artistic works is an imperative of our time and contributes to improving the quality of educational programmes. Receipts from foreign authors and organisations are relevant and high-priority, as their processing ensures a high level of accreditation requirements. Thanks to the donations from publishing houses, public organisations, and individuals, the diverse stock collections of the university library are being updated qualitatively.

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Джерела актуальної інформації університетської книгозбірні під час повномасштабного російського вторгнення в Україну

Мета статті полягає у висвітленні особливостей процесу комплектування університетської наукової бібліотеки в умовах воєнного часу та якісного задоволення читацьких запитів за допомогою фондових колекцій. Об'єктом дослідження стали книжкові та журнальні колекції, що поповнили бібліотечні фонди університету за 2022–2024 роки. Нові надходження розглянуто за видами, тематикою, видавництвами та джерелами. **Методика.** Для створення цілісної картини розвитку документного ресурсу бібліотеки за певний час використано аналітико-синтетичний, системно-структурний, порівняльний та статистичний методи наукових досліджень. **Результати.** Результати дослідження свідчать про те, що відбір та аналіз надходжень бібліотеки університету під час воєнних дій доводить першочергове значення поповнення книжкового фонду українськомовними різногалузевими джерелами актуальної інформації. Це сприяє якісному інформаційному забезпеченню навчального процесу та наукової діяльності в повному обсязі. **Висновки.** Попри труднощі, бібліотечні фонди як інформаційна система розвиваються й оновлюються. Проведений аналіз дозволив уявити картину стану української видавничої справи та потужної підтримки університетських бібліотек.

Ключові слова: університетська бібліотека; фонди; нові надходження; повномасштабна російсько-українська війна 2022–2024 років; освітній процес; Україна

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